

A Study on the Evaluation of Case Teaching Effectiveness of "Sharing Economics" in the Context of Digital Economy

Jun Yu

School of Economics, Anhui University of Finance & Economics, Bengbu, Anhui 233030, China

Abstract: *The ultimate goal of case-based teaching design is to promote the cultivation of professional talents, and its effectiveness must be evaluated in conjunction with student interaction and feedback. The cultivation of professional talents needs to keep pace with the times. In the era of the internet and big data, economic and social development demands that management talents not only master the basic theories of economics and management, but also acquire knowledge of emerging disciplines such as big data and modern information technology. Based on this, this paper will conduct a systematic study on the evaluation of the effectiveness of case-based teaching in "Sharing Economics" within the current digital economy context, combined with teaching practice, in order to provide as much reference as possible for other courses.*

Keywords: Digital economy; Sharing economy; Case study teaching; Effectiveness evaluation.

1. Introduction

With the emergence of various sharing economy products, investor enthusiasm for the sharing economy has been growing. The sharing economy is seen as a viable means to alleviate resource constraints and overcome limitations in economic development. The capital market's favor towards "sharing" is a major reason why many entrepreneurs are joining the sharing economy movement. According to the "China Sharing Economy Development Report (2023)" released by the E-commerce Research Center of the State Information Center, in 2022, the transaction scale of my country's sharing economy market was approximately 3.832 trillion yuan, a year-on-year increase of about 3.9%. The imbalance in the development of the sharing economy in different fields is becoming increasingly prominent. Influenced by various factors such as the capital market situation and regulatory policies, the market structure of the sharing economy in many fields is constantly changing.

The rapid growth of the digital economy and the sharing economy has created a large demand for innovative talents in the sharing economy. However, there is currently a significant shortage of innovative talents who understand both the basic theories of the digital economy and are well-versed in the practical application of sharing economy cases. This will, to some extent, restrict the healthy and vigorous development of the digital economy and the sharing economy industry. Of course, the ultimate goal of case-based teaching design is to cultivate professional talents, and the effectiveness of case-based teaching design needs to be tested in conjunction with feedback from student interaction. The cultivation of professional talents must keep pace with the times. In the era of the internet and big

data, economic and social development demands more than just mastery of economics and management theories from business and management professionals; it also requires knowledge of emerging disciplines such as big data and modern information technology. Furthermore, ideological and political education in courses is indispensable.

Based on this, this paper will conduct a systematic study on the evaluation of the case-based teaching effectiveness of "Sharing Economics" within the current digital economy context, combined with teaching practice, in order to provide as much reference as possible for other courses.

2. Literature Review

Based on the research focus, this paper intends to sort out the existing literature from the following two aspects: The first aspect involves the digital economy and the sharing economy and their relationship. The term "sharing economy" first appeared in a paper by Felson and Spaeth in 1978. Scholars discussed car sharing at that time, but due to the objective conditions at that time, it was difficult to realize the lifestyle concept they advocated [1]. By 2008, the impact of the international financial crisis caused idle resources, which made people's desire for additional income more urgent. The maturity of mobile Internet technology made the development of the sharing economy increasingly feasible in terms of technology. Under the combined influence of subjective and objective conditions, the sharing economy has developed vigorously in the past ten years. The hot development of the sharing economy has aroused the research enthusiasm of scholars. In recent years, the research hotspots have mainly focused on how the sharing economy can expand domestic demand, promote common prosperity, and realize a low-carbon economy [2-3]. Since Tapscott proposed the concept of "digital economy" in 1996, his research has roughly gone through three stages: information economy, Internet economy and new economy. Today, the concept of digital economy mainly refers to new economic activities that take digital information as an important resource, the Internet platform as an important carrier, and a series of new models and new business forms as manifestations [4]. In recent years, the research hotspots of scholars have mainly focused on how the digital economy can empower rural revitalization, accelerate the formation of new quality productivity, promote high-quality development, and advance Chinese-style modernization [5].

The second aspect involves case teaching and flipped classroom and the combination of the two. The case teaching method originated from Harvard Law School in the 1870s and became increasingly popular after being promoted by the business school of the same school. Its application in business majors has been more than 100 years. Since the introduction of the case teaching method, domestic case teaching has gone through a process from imitation to innovation [6]. Many scholars believe that the "post-00s" college students of the new era were born in the Internet era, and case teaching must adapt to the emotional and behavioral characteristics of college students in the new era under the digital economy industry-education integration environment [7]. As a new teaching model, the flipped classroom subverts the traditional classroom teaching model of "lecture first and then practice" and flips the order of knowledge transmission and classroom activities [8].

Existing literature has explored the design of case teaching from multiple perspectives such as curriculum ideological and political education and innovative talent training. However, both courses and textbooks on the sharing economy are severely lacking in China, resulting in a scarcity of literature discussing the evaluation of case-based teaching effectiveness in sharing economy. Therefore, this paper aims to explore the evaluation of case-based teaching effectiveness in sharing economy from the perspective of the digital economy and in conjunction with teaching practice.

3. Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Case-based Teaching of "Sharing Economics" in the Context of the Digital Economy

3.1 Digital Economy and Sharing Economy

The digital economy, strictly speaking, is an economic activity that uses data resources as a factor of production, the internet as a carrier, and communication technology as a driving force, manifesting in numerous new models and business formats. It encompasses all aspects of production, circulation, and consumption, powerfully propelling the economy towards networking, intelligence, and digitalization. Compared to the traditional economy, the core characteristics of the digital economy are mainly reflected in the following aspects: First, data-driven characteristics. Unlike the traditional economic theory where land, labor, and capital are considered equal, data has become a crucial factor of production. The data collection, analysis, and application processes can improve production efficiency and drive innovation. The digital economy relies on information and communication technologies, such as cloud computing and blockchain. These technologies not only effectively improve the overall operational efficiency of the social economy but also promote the further expansion of new industries and models. Second, digital platform characteristics. The digital economy primarily operates through internet platforms, such as social media platforms and digital payment platforms. These platforms can effectively reduce transaction costs, improve matching efficiency, and create more employment opportunities. Third, sharing and collaboration characteristics. The digital economy emphasizes open innovation and resource sharing, much like open-source software and remote collaborative work models. It lowers the barriers to entry for various economic entities and improves resource utilization efficiency. Fourthly, it possesses instantaneous and global characteristics. The digital economy accelerates the flow of information, enabling transactions and decisions to be completed almost instantly. This leads to more intense market competition, requiring businesses to adapt to changes in the external environment at a faster pace. The digital economy has become a significant driving force for global economic growth, not only changing traditional business models but also profoundly impacting social governance and individual lifestyles. In the future, with further technological development, the scale and influence of the digital economy will further increase.

The sharing economy primarily relies on the internet and digital technology, connecting supply and demand through digital platforms to provide goods and services in a peer-to-peer manner, maximizing resource utilization efficiency. While the sharing economy is an innovative business model that brings considerable convenience and economic value, it still requires continuous optimization to ensure its healthy and sustainable development. The core characteristics of the sharing economy are mainly manifested in the following aspects: First, high resource utilization efficiency. The key to the sharing economy lies in activating idle resources. Individuals or enterprises can share resources that have not been effectively utilized, thereby reducing resource waste. Second, digital platforms as a medium. The sharing economy is highly dependent on digital platforms, relying on them to connect supply and demand. Platforms endow the sharing economy with various functions such as resource matching, transaction payment, and after-sales evaluation. Third, disintermediation and reintermediation occur. Traditional economic models often require tangible intermediaries to match trading parties, but the sharing economy matches trading parties through digital platforms, which effectively reduces intermediate links and lowers transaction costs. Fourth, users have a dual role. Users in the sharing economy are called prosumers; they are both producers and consumers of goods. Fifth, flexibility. This model of the sharing economy is usually used according to demand and consumed according to quantity; users do not need to own the assets. Sixth, scale and network effects exist. The sharing economy relies on the scale of its users; the more users, the higher the value of the platform.

Driven by the digital economy, the sharing economy, as a new economic model, has achieved tangible development results in recent years. The sharing economy leverages internet platforms to achieve resource sharing, exchange, and efficient utilization, improving resource allocation efficiency and creating a win-win opportunity for both producers and consumers. Within the context of the digital economy, the sharing economy fully utilizes the advantages of platforms and technological innovations to promote the effective allocation of various resources. First, the continuous development of digital technology provides strong support for the sharing economy. The widespread application of technologies such as the internet and big data has made information transmission more convenient, data analysis more accurate, and the matching of supply and demand more effective. These technological advancements have led to the vigorous development of the platform economy. In many fields such as transportation, accommodation, and education, the sharing economy can achieve efficient resource matching through platforms. Second, the continuous development of the digital economy has effectively lowered the barriers to participation in the sharing economy. Traditional economic models often rely heavily on intermediaries and conventional transaction methods. However, in the context of the digital economy, platform-based sharing economy models can reduce transaction costs by eliminating intermediaries, thus enabling more individuals and businesses to participate. This elimination of intermediaries not only improves efficiency but also stimulates new business opportunities and drives the creation of more innovative services. Furthermore, the rapid development of the sharing economy in the digital age has significantly impacted traditional industries. For example, ride-sharing and shared accommodation, through intelligent resource scheduling and precise location, achieve operational efficiency levels unattainable by traditional industries. This not only enhances the consumer experience but also provides new revenue streams for businesses, powerfully promoting industrial upgrading. However, the rapid development of the sharing economy in the digital economy also faces some challenges. On the one hand, data security and privacy protection have become key concerns for users and regulatory agencies. On the other hand, competition between platforms and related governance issues must be addressed urgently. How to promote the innovative development of the sharing economy while ensuring its healthy and sustainable development has become a crucial issue of great concern to all parties. Against the backdrop of the digital economy, the sharing economy has continued to develop, bringing about significant changes to the economy and society. On the one hand, it has effectively improved resource utilization efficiency; on the other hand, it has fully stimulated the vitality of the market, and simultaneously promoted innovation in new business models and service formats. However, throughout its development, how to properly balance innovation and regulation, how to effectively protect users' rights, and how to effectively maintain social fairness remain issues that require continuous exploration and resolution. Observing the core characteristics of both the digital economy and the sharing economy, it is not difficult to find many commonalities, and the relationship between the two is extremely close. In fact, the sharing economy is an important component of the digital economy, and its essence relies on the support of digital platforms and data technologies. Therefore, the growth of the sharing economy is inseparable from the strong support provided by the construction of digital economic infrastructure. The digital economy is undoubtedly a very important driving force for the development of the sharing economy. Digital technologies are constantly being integrated in the industrial and social development fields. This integration has greatly promoted the innovation of the sharing economy business model, and thus promoted the gradual penetration of the sharing economy into all aspects of social production and life.

3.2 Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Case-based Teaching in the Sharing Economy

With the continuous development and evolution of internet technology, the sharing economy has become a crucial component of the global economy. Platforms like Uber, Airbnb, and Didi, representing the sharing economy model, are fundamentally changing traditional industrial structures and consumer

behavior. The course "Sharing Economics" aims to enable students to fully understand the basic principles, business models, regulatory frameworks, and socio-economic impacts of the sharing economy. To effectively enhance students' practical skills and stimulate their innovative thinking, case study teaching has become a widely used and common teaching method in sharing economics courses.

In my years of teaching practice, case study teaching has indeed helped students gain a deeper understanding of the core concepts of the sharing economy and has also promoted their critical thinking and innovation abilities. The sharing economy involves many controversial issues, such as labor rights protection, platform responsibilities, and market monopolies. Case study teaching encourages students to analyze these issues from various perspectives, thereby improving their critical thinking skills. For example, in discussions about the regulation of Airbnb, some students supported stronger government oversight, believing it would protect tenants' rights. Others, however, held different views, arguing that excessive regulation could stifle innovation. Through such discussions, students could weigh the needs of various stakeholders and propose more feasible policy recommendations.

The course "Sharing Economics" has consistently used the flipped classroom approach for many years, along with group discussion and practice activities. This arrangement aims to encourage more active student participation, enhance teamwork skills, and deepen their understanding of real-world sharing economy cases. Educational philosophies are constantly evolving, and information technology is rapidly advancing. In this context, traditional teaching models are revealing their shortcomings, particularly in cultivating independent learning, stimulating innovative thinking, and developing practical skills. Against this backdrop, the flipped classroom has emerged as a new teaching model and is gradually gaining wider application in the education field. Furthermore, case-based teaching, as a teaching method that emphasizes practicality and problem-solving skills, has significant advantages in the field of education. Combining the flipped classroom and case-based teaching can fully leverage the strengths of both methods, effectively improve students' learning motivation, enhance their innovation abilities, and improve their practical skills.

In traditional classroom teaching, teachers typically play the role of knowledge transmitters, while students are generally in a passive state of receiving information. The flipped classroom reverses the order of classroom learning and pre-class preparation. Students can use self-study resources such as pre-class videos, literature, and online materials to master basic knowledge and theories, while classroom time is mainly used for discussion, application, and deepening of knowledge. Under this model, students' initiative in learning is greatly enhanced. When the flipped classroom and case-based teaching are combined, students can learn about the background, key issues, and related theoretical knowledge of cases outside of class through multimedia materials, interactive platforms, and other means. In this way, they can focus their energy in the classroom on how to analyze and solve practical problems. In this way, students can not only participate more actively in the learning process, but also deepen their understanding of knowledge through discussion and exchange, thereby improving their ability to solve practical problems. Case-based teaching itself emphasizes the analysis and discussion of real-world situations, which effectively stimulates students' critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. The flipped classroom provides students with more time and space, allowing them to bring questions and thoughts arising during classroom learning to classroom discussions for in-depth exploration. After students have mastered relevant knowledge through self-study in the flipped classroom, they can analyze specific cases in class, proposing different viewpoints and solutions. This discussion and analysis based on real-world situations helps students develop their decision-making abilities in complex and ambiguous environments, and cultivates their critical thinking, innovative thinking, and teamwork skills. The key to the flipped classroom is encouraging students to acquire knowledge through self-directed learning, collaborative learning, and inquiry-based learning, while

case-based teaching focuses on in-depth research into specific problems. By combining these two approaches, students can not only engage in self-directed learning outside the classroom through research and online discussions, but also integrate theoretical knowledge with practical experience in the classroom through group collaboration and case discussions. This learning process often requires an interdisciplinary perspective and comprehensive abilities. For example, when analyzing a business case involving multiple fields, students need to apply knowledge from economics and management, as well as theories from sociology, psychology, and other disciplines. This interdisciplinary integration not only broadens students' knowledge but also helps them cultivate more innovative and practical problem-solving skills.

The flipped classroom emphasizes student interaction and hands-on practice. Teachers design challenging questions to encourage students to think deeply and analyze cases in group discussions. During these discussions, students must analyze the cases using theoretical knowledge and provide solutions to the practical problems encountered. Throughout this process, the teacher acts as a guide and facilitator, not merely a transmitter of knowledge. Through various methods such as group collaboration, role-playing, and scenario simulation, students can analyze cases from multiple perspectives and levels, thereby cultivating their innovative thinking and teamwork spirit. The flipped classroom is not limited to in-class interaction; post-class extension activities are equally important. Taking case-based teaching as an example, teachers can help students apply the knowledge and skills learned in class to real-world situations by assigning homework, arranging project reports, or conducting further case analysis. Such post-class reflection and practical operation can deepen students' understanding of knowledge and help them more effectively combine theory and practice, thereby improving their practical skills.

While combining the flipped classroom and case-based teaching has many advantages, some challenges have also arisen in its practical application. On the one hand, students' self-learning abilities and self-discipline vary significantly; some students may not be able to complete pre-class learning tasks effectively, thus affecting the effectiveness of classroom discussions. In such situations, teachers can ensure students are well-prepared before class by designing relatively interactive pre-class tasks, such as online quizzes, discussion topics, or group collaborations. On the other hand, effectively guiding students to analyze and discuss case studies in class presents another challenge. Teachers can ensure every student actively participates and fully utilizes their thinking and creativity during discussions by clearly defining questions, assigning roles appropriately, and organizing group collaborations.

Of course, in more concrete implementation, there is indeed the issue of some students "free-riding." Therefore, teachers must carefully observe the specific division of labor among group members, the discussion process, and the actual collaboration. If free-riding occurs, timely intervention is necessary. If student groups encounter problems they cannot solve, teachers need to provide appropriate guidance. However, throughout this guidance process, the teacher's role is only to guide and inspire; they must never overstep their bounds and solve the problems for the students.

Overall, case-based teaching has yielded positive results in the sharing economy course. It has enhanced students' understanding of the knowledge, fostered critical thinking, stimulated innovation, and promoted teamwork. While some challenges remain, continuous improvements, such as updating case studies, strengthening data analysis, and implementing interdisciplinary collaborations, can further improve its effectiveness. The sharing economy is an emerging economic model, and its teaching methods should therefore be continuously innovated to cultivate more innovative talents capable of meeting the needs of future economic development.

4. Conclusion

This paper, within the context of the current digital economy and combined with teaching practice, systematically studies the evaluation of case-based teaching effectiveness in "Sharing Economics," aiming to provide as much reference as possible for other courses.

Case studies in sharing economics must be up-to-date. The sharing economy is an emerging economic model that achieves efficient resource allocation through digital platforms, internet technology, and community collaboration. Its core concept is that "the right to use is more important than ownership," promoting overall social benefits through the sharing of resources, services, and information. The development of the sharing economy is closely linked to technological advancements, changes in market demand, and adjustments in policies and regulations. Therefore, related case studies must be up-to-date to accurately reflect the latest trends and challenges in this field. The key to the sharing economy lies in technological innovation and changing user needs; therefore, case studies cannot remain on outdated business models but must closely follow the industry's cutting-edge dynamics. The sharing economy is highly dependent on technological development, especially in the application of technologies such as big data, artificial intelligence, and blockchain. Therefore, case studies should also demonstrate how the latest technologies impact the sharing economy model. As a dynamically evolving business model, the sharing economy requires case studies that are up-to-date to reflect the latest changes in technology, market conditions, policies, and user behavior. Only in this way can researchers and practitioners gain accurate insights, thereby guiding the industry's continued innovation and optimization.

References

- [1] Felson, M., & Spaeth, J. L. (1978). Community structure and collaborative consumption: A routine activity approach. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 21(4), 614–624.
- [2] Gan, X., Wei, Z., & Di, X. (2022). How do technology-enabled bike-sharing services improve urban air pollution? Empirical evidence from China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 379(1).
- [3] Ni, Z., & Li, C. (2022). Carbon emission reduction by bicycle-sharing in China. *Energies*, 15(14), 5136–5136.
- [4] S., J., H., J., & L., K. (2020). Digitization and phase transitions in platform organizing logics: Evidence from the process automation industry. *MIS Quarterly*, 44(1), 129–153.
- [5] C., T., K., M., & M., S., et al. (2021). Digital technologies, innovation, and skills: Emerging trajectories and challenges. *Research Policy*, 50(7).
- [6] Green, C., Eady, M., & Andersen, P. (2018). Preparing quality teachers: Bridging the gap between tertiary experiences and classroom realities. *Teaching & Learning Inquiry*, (1).
- [7] Hoffmann, C. P., Lutz, C., & Meckel, M. (2014). Digital natives or digital immigrants? The impact of user characteristics on online trust. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 31(3), 138–171.
- [8] Steffens, K. (2015). Competences, learning theories and MOOC s: Recent developments in lifelong learning. *European Journal of Education*, 50(1), 41–59.